

A Study on The Awareness and Knowledge about Wealth Management among People in Kanpur City

Paper Id : 19059 Submission Date : 2024-07-10 Acceptance Date : 2024-07-19 Publication Date : 2024-07-22
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13148996

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Abstract The study aims to improve people's understanding and awareness of wealth management. Finding out how investors of different genders, ages, and income levels decide to invest in different routes is the main goal of the study. Data for the study are gathered by a questionnaire survey from 60 respondents who are working professionals or income earners. Data is collected by the 'convenience sampling method' In this study, a descriptive research design was employed. Just 64 percent of the total respondents claim to be knowledgeable about wealth management. Furthermore, a large number of them are conscious yet lack the necessary word knowledge. As respondents' preferred investments in their portfolios included PPF, FDs, life insurance, gold, and other risk-free assets, we can conclude that these are some well-liked sources aside from savings accounts. Savings percentages generally show the amount of risk a person is willing to take. A high saving ratio was linked to a high risk, while a low risk was linked to a high saving ratio. The risk increases with the size of the return. The most relied source for information about wealth management among the respondents is family and friends showing the trust in them, but also creates problems if the advice doesn't go as planned which most definitely should change because they give advice based on their situation. Many respondents also rely on financial advisors and books.

Keywords Wealth Management, Respondents, Life Insurance.

Introduction

We all have dreams, don't we? Whether it's finally owning that cozy house, launching our dream business, exploring exotic destinations, or just ensuring our family's future is secure. But dreams come with a price tag, and that's where the nitty-gritty of finances comes into play. Think of wealth management as having your own personal financial coach. They're there to guide you through the maze of banking, investment choices, taxes, and making your money grow over time. Warren Buffet, the legendary investor, always talks about understanding stocks as if you're buying into a business – that's the kind of savvy advice wealth managers can offer.

For most of us, building wealth isn't just about stashing away cash. It's about making that money work for us. That's where the magic of wealth management kicks in. Your advisor crafts a plan that suits your lifestyle and aspirations, helping your money grow through savvy investments and smart tax strategies.

But let's face it, navigating finances can be daunting. That's why having a team of experts who understand your goals and challenges are invaluable. They'll tailor a plan just for you, tracking your progress every step of the way and adjusting as needed to ensure you reach those financial milestones.

So, whether you're dreaming of a tropical getaway or securing your family's future, remember: with the light guidance, your financial goals are within reach.

Objective of study

1. To evaluate the extent to which the target audience understands various aspects of wealth management, including investment options, risk management, tax planning, retirement planning, estate planning, and other relevant topics.
2. To identify the areas where there is a lack of understanding or misinformation regarding wealth management concepts and strategies.

3. To explore emerging trends, challenges, and opportunities within the wealth management industry that may impact individuals' awareness and decision-making processes.
4. To offer recommendations and strategies to enhance awareness and education efforts related to wealth management, both at the individual and institutional levels.
5. To compare awareness levels across different demographics, regions, or socio-economic groups to identify disparities and target specific areas for improvement.
6. To assess the potential impact of increased awareness and education on individuals' financial well-being, investment behavior, and overall wealth management success.

Review of Literature

According to Chetana Asbe and team (2024), in 'Wealth: Grow It and Protect It' by Lucas, there's a guide for family businesses to thrive across generations. This research looks at how 160 Indian family businesses are doing with Lucas's ideas. Turns out, there are challenges, especially for medium-sized ones. The next generation might feel left out, and founders might hesitate to bring in help when needed. The suggestion? A more inclusive approach to passing on the business, with open discussions and plans for the next generation. By following Lucas's framework and being more inclusive, Indian family businesses can keep their legacy alive while boosting the economy.

According to Mr. Aakash Sharma and team (2023) around the world, both investors and governments are increasingly stressing the importance of environmentally responsible finance. They're pushing for investors to look beyond just the risks and returns of their investments, recognizing the broader benefits of considering environmental impacts. This shift towards responsible investment not only benefits the planet but also enhances India's global reputation. A recent study delved into how Indian financial organizations are approaching corporate responsibility and sustainability reporting. They examined the annual reports of five emerging companies in detail: Bajaj Finance Limited, IIFL Wealth Management Limited, Indiabulls Housing Finance Limited, Home First Finance Company India Limited, and Nahar Capital and Financial Services Limited. The findings revealed a growing trend of sustainable finance practices across India's financial sector. Moreover, the study highlighted the need for policy changes and reforms to ensure the long-term growth of financial markets in India. These changes are crucial for making the region more appealing to potential investors. The study emphasized the importance of these adjustments, recognizing them as key factors for the sector's future success.

According to Singh, B. and Singh, M. (2023), financial illiteracy continues to be a pressing global issue, despite all the progress we've seen in financial markets. It hits hardest among marginalized groups who face social and economic challenges, making it difficult for them to access professional financial guidance due to financial constraints. In the study, researchers focused on understanding the financial literacy levels among marginalized communities living in hilly regions. They found that financial literacy is notably low among scheduled tribes in these areas. Factors like education, income, family dynamics, and access to the internet were identified as significant influencers on their financial literacy levels. Recognizing these factors is crucial because it helps us tailor interventions to address the specific needs of these communities. By improving financial literacy, we can empower marginalized groups to make better financial choices, ultimately contributing to their financial well-being and resilience.

According to Ankita Bhatia and team's research (2023), this study delves into how innovation, particularly digital innovation, is reshaping wealth management. Focusing on the impact of robo- advisory services on investment decision-making and behavioral biases like overconfidence and loss aversion, it fills a gap in research, especially in developing countries like India. The authors discovered that these biases notably affect investment decisions, despite the use of robo-advisory services. In simpler terms, even with digital assistance, investors still fall prey to their own biases, like thinking they know more than they do or being overly afraid of losses.

According to Solomon and Priya (2019), the study explores how women are increasingly taking charge of family wealth, highlighting the need for tailored investment options. Conducted with 250 women aged 30 to 65, including professionals and homemakers, it investigates their investment preferences and decision-making factors. The aim is to provide insights for wealth managers to better serve this growing demographic and bridge the "experience gaps" in the field, promoting inclusivity and empowerment.

Methodology

A survey was conducted via Google Forms to collect data from participants, constituting primary data for the study. The survey was administered online through a questionnaire, employing a random sampling technique to select the sample. Data interpretation was conducted through graphical representations and percentage analyses.

The primary focus of the research articulated in this article concerns various aspects of wealth management. "Wealth management" refers to the administration of an individual's diverse forms of wealth, encompassing cash and asset management, risk management, estate planning, tax planning, budgeting, future planning, spending control, retirement planning, and a range of other planning aspects. A secondary objective of this inquiry is to assess and explore the wealth management practices, knowledge, and awareness among Indian households. Among the secondary objectives is the examination of preferences regarding low-risk or high-risk investments, alongside an evaluation of individuals' risk-taking propensity, their ability to manage risks, comprehension of budgeting, spending management, and related domains.

Research, as defined, entails the process of conducting in-depth analysis of data to unveil actual outcomes, solutions, and societal benefits, among other objectives. Various classifications such as descriptive research, exploratory research, and cross-sectional research characterize research endeavors. A substantial portion of the investigation adheres to clearly delineated Primary and Secondary Objectives. Primary Objectives command primary focus during this investigation, while Secondary Objectives assume a subsequent level of importance.

The pivotal phases of the research process encompass data collection and subsequent analysis. Primary data, collected firsthand, and secondary data, recycled from past sources, constitute the two types of information sources. Primary data may be quantitative or qualitative and can be acquired through methods such as questionnaire administration or interviews. Secondary data, on the other hand, comprises information gleaned from sources such as newspapers, literature, journals, and the like.

Analysis

The method that had been chosen for data collection is by running a survey through Google form, The link of which is provided ahead. The collected data of 60 peoples is being shown below in various forms of charts along with the interpretation and analysis to follow.

Demographic Details of Surveyed Audience

Age Group
60 responses

Desired Savings Percentage

Desired savings percentage
60 responses

Gender
60 responses

Qualification
60 responses

Percentage of Income Invested

Percentage of income invested
60 responses

Do You Have A Proper Financial Planning

Do y have a proper financial planning
60 responses

How Often Do You Review Your Financial Situation And Investment Portfolio?

How often do you review your financial situation and investment portfolio?
 60 responses

The Respondants' Level of Knowledge Wealth Management

The Respondents' Level of Knowledge Regarding Wealth Management

How Important Is It For You To Seek Professional Advice For Wealth Management?

How important is it for you to seek professional advice for wealth management?
 60 responses

What Sources Do You Primarily Rely On For Information About WealthManagement?

What sources do you primarily rely on for information about wealth management?

60 responses

Findings

Demographic profile of respondents

The survey attracted younger participants, with 56.7% aged between 18 and 30 year highlighting the significant interest in wealth management among younger demographics. The educational background of respondents is notably high, suggesting a well-educated cohort engaging in wealth management.

The Respondents' Level of Knowledge Regarding Wealth Management

The survey showed a mixed reaction of respondents on weather wealth management is only useful for businessmen or if its for everyone. Most people agreed that wealth management can be time and cost consuming. Most people agreed that it is the best way to utilize savings. There was a mixed reaction on weather its only useful for rich where most people were neutral or disagreed but a lot of them agreed. Most respondents agreed that it is useful for all.

"Its useful only for businessman": Strongly agree (19.7%), Agree (26.2%), Neutral (24.6%), Disagree (19.7%), Strongly disagree (9.8%)

"Time and cost consuming": Strongly agree (18%), Agree (39.3%), Neutral (29.5%), Disagree (9.8%),

Strongly disagree (3.3%)

"Best way to utilize savings": Strongly agree (34.4%), Agree (39.3%), Neutral (22.9%), Disagree (1.6%), Strongly disagree (1.6%)

"It's useful for only rich": Strongly agree (9.8%), Agree (22.9%), Neutral (26.2%), Disagree (26.2%), Strongly disagree (15.6%)

"It's useful for all": Strongly agree (42.6%), Agree (27.9%), Neutral (24.6%), Disagree (3.3%),

Strongly disagree (1.6%)

Percentage of saved and invested income

Majority of the respondent's desired percentage of savings was 10 to 20% and 20 to 30%. Most of the respondents invested income ranged from 5 to 15%. People were mostly divided on if they have a proper financial planning or not.

Most relied sources for wealth management advice

The most relied source for information about wealth management among the respondents is family and friends showing the trust in them, but also creates problems if the advice doesn't go as planned which most definitely should change because they give advice based on their situation. Many respondents also rely on financial advisors and books.

Financial Advisors: 49.2%

Conclusion

The survey conducted provides a comprehensive look at the behaviors, preferences, and perceptions of individuals regarding wealth management. Educated individuals predominantly engaged in academia or early-stage professional careers, the findings reflect a demographic that is both cautious and strategic in its investment approaches.

The survey also highlighted a diverse reliance on recommendations, ranging from financial experts to personal acquaintances, though with varying degrees of trust. This reflects a cautious but open approach to navigating complex investment landscapes, pointing towards a need for credible, accessible investment advice tailored to young investors.

In conclusion, the behavior of these wealth management participants indicates a trend towards thoughtful, informed investment strategies that consider a mix of financial indicators.

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